

The Role of Lean Leadership in Building Organizational Reputation A Study on Pharmaceutical Industry in Egypt

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Abstract

The objective of the research is to identify the role of Lean Leadership (LL) in building Organizational Reputation (OR) at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt. The research population consists of all employees at the pharmaceutical industry in Egypt. Due to time and cost constraints, the researcher adopted a sampling method to collect data for the study. The appropriate statistical methods were used to analyze the data and test the hypotheses.

The research has reached a number of results, the most important of which are: (1) the results of the data analysis indicated that the relationship between LL and OR was positive. This means that the employees awareness which has a good LL, lowers their feelings about their belonging to that organization. This is directly reflected in increasing their commitment and thus achieving the good reputation of the organization, (2) the employees realize that the organization is the place where they work. Therefore they try to maintain the reputation of the organization through their commitment, and they do not wish to detract from the organization in any way. This is because they consider themselves to be an important part of the fabric of the organization, (3) the analysis showed that the change in the level of employee awareness of LL is reflected in further levels of OR enhancement by employees, and (4) the analysis showed that the change in the availability of LL is reflected in the further change in the levels of organizational commitment of employees and this effect also leads to a change in organizational reputation levels.

The research concluded that: (1) the necessity of investing the organization in the abilities of the employees in terms of the availability of the LL by respecting the capabilities of the employees of the organization such as finding a wage system commensurate with their efforts and urging participation in decision making within the organization, (2) adopting effective communication methods that enhance the importance of distinguished employees and build a system through which values can be established among the employees within the organization, and the need to be committed to exchanging positive respect for the characteristics of the employees and avoiding all that contributes to reducing the personal status of the employee, (3) the need for the organization to reflect a positive image of the members of society by disseminating positive information about its good reputation. The dissemination of information through seminars and conferences can enhance the employees' awareness of the status of the organization in society in general, (4) the organization should focus on the importance of social values in the organization and the need for employees to feel proud when their personal values dissolve in social values, which enhance their levels of commitment to the organization, (5) develop an appropriate strategy to manage and consolidate the concepts of LL, OR and highlight its importance, programs and applications through training programs, panel discussions, seminars and scientific conferences, and (6) The organization should pay attention to the process of creating a common vision among employees to enhance OR through LL, and encourage employees to make suggestions to develop their abilities and improve their performance, which makes the organization in a distinguished position compared to others in the same field.

1. Introduction

Substantial empirical evidence from at least the past 20 years shows that leadership matters (Yukl, 2010). There is wide consensus that leadership is important or in fact essential to achieve organizational success (Liker, 2009).

There are several different theories and models have evolved that describe what a leader should or should not do to achieve best results for the organization (Alvesson & Sveningsson S., (2007).).

During the 1980's and 1990's leadership development was strongly influenced by the direction of leadership called transformational leadership, a leadership style that enhances the motivation, morale, and performance of co-workers through a variety of mechanisms (Larsson & Kallenberg, 2003).

Parallel to the leadership stream, Toyota attracted world attention by producing better cars than others and lean management – a product developed by Toyota Production Systems – started to gain increasing interest (Emiliani, 2008).

Lean Leadership (LL) shows that management is not separated from leadership by definitions. Beliefs, behaviors, and competencies that demonstrate respect for people, motivate people, improve business conditions, minimize or eliminate organizational politics, ensure effective utilization of resources, and eliminate confusion and rework". The definition includes critical aspects of leadership that other definitions have not considered (Emiliani, 2008).

The advantages of LL in the organization vary and can be illustrated as follows (1) LL achieves a better understanding of what roles they are assigned and better achievement of agility applications within the organization, in a manner that helps to spread a culture of agile behavior through the exchange of information among all employees of the organization, (2) The lean thinking of leadership implies that individuals in the organization constitute intellectual

capital, and their role must be clear and effective in decision-making, participation in problem solving, and constructive suggestions, (3) LL achieves high levels of agile behaviors that must demonstrate that there are relationships and relationships between the leader and employees based on mutual respect, and (4) LL takes control over time by efficiently and efficiently exploiting time (Ljungblom, 2012; Beal, 2008; Testani & Ramakrishnan, 2011).

The concepts of organizational reputation plays a central role in multiple studies in the scientific literature. Organizational reputation is a concept that lacks a common degreed definition up till now, however several suggestions are given. Several scholars argue that organizational reputation describes the organizations overall attractiveness (Barnett et al., 2006; Fombrun, 2012).

Organizations Reputation (OR) is used to refer to the term “employer brand” (Mosley, 2015; Cable & Turban, 2003). In other words, organizational reputation is an integral part of employer branding (Yüksel, 2015).

Organizational reputation is become an increasingly important concept in literature since the competition for attracting the best talented employees is in full swing (Backhaus & Tikoo, 2004; Cable & Turban, 2001).

Organizational reputation serves as an intangible asset that allows stakeholders to differentiate an organization that has a high reputation from organizations without this asset (Pfarrer et al., 2010). In this way, a high reputation can provide an organization with specific advantages, such as better access to resources, the ability to employ high-quality workers, and greater chances of financial success (Deephouse, 2000; Rindova et al., 2005).

2. Lean Leadership

2.1. Lean Leadership Concept

LL is the art of easy dealing with all employees of the organization. It is characterized by high levels of patience in terms of individuals, training and development, as well as firmness in problem solving (Aij & Lohman, 2016).

LL is the way to improve organizational performance, a philosophy of continuous improvement, which requires the commitment and participation of all staff in the organization (Jurado, 2014).

LL aims to produce products and services at the lowest cost and as quickly as possible, focusing on efficiency, minimizing losses and eliminating non-value added activities to improve speed and increase productivity. One of the basic principles of LL is to seek perfection in a constantly changing world. This philosophy is based on the fact that everyone in the organization needs to be fully involved in its principles, and that it is a relatively simple philosophy, but the challenges lie in its implementation. So, managers need to change their way of managing employees, because changing management is the most difficult part of transforming into a LL concept, rather than just changing processes, tools and systems (Sparrow & Otaye, 2014; Nylund, 2013).

LL is a multidimensional concept that requires considerable effort, whether it involves the successful implementation of LL elements, the implementation of LL practices to support the operational aspects of the organization, or through long-term improvements (Teich et al., 2013).

LL is an organized way to achieve better business performance through mutual respect and confidence between the leader and staff of the organization (Dombrowski & Mielke, 2013).

LL is one of modern variables that have attracted the attention of researchers, due to the great role played by leadership in achieving organizational success. LL is the behaviors that add or create value to the individual and the organization in which he works. In other words, LL is behavior that avoids loss of resources for the organization (Ljungblom, 2012).

Attention has continued to be given to many kinds of leadership, such as spiritual, authentic, servant and other leadership. Researchers have benefited from the content of agility in the production process to the need to refer to the LL. The lean leader has certain behaviors, including helping and respecting individuals, supporting them, focusing on work, and having a clear vision, clear goals and continuous commitment (Puvanasvaran, 2012).

LL is a philosophy through which the organization aims to maximize value to its customers by reducing losses or waste, and that this philosophy is a way that is very focused on customer thinking and can be seen as a tool to create more value, not just a tool used by the organization to get rid of Losses or waste. To be successful, the philosophy of the concept of LL must be fully accepted and operated by the organization as a whole (Nicholas, 2011).

LL is the behavior that brings value to the organization, works to reduce levels of waste associated with good ideas, unproductive relationships, and low levels of collaboration among employees in the organization. In other words, LL is the key tool to improve the quality of products and services, reduce costs, reduce time, increase market share of the organization, and develop new products and services (Emiliani, 2006).

The researcher sees the concept of LL from two perspectives, the first from a philosophical perspective on guidelines and overall goals, and second through a practical perspective on a set of practices, tools, or management techniques that correspond to the philosophical perspective.

2.2. Lean Leadership Dimensions

The dimensions of LL are six dimensions. They are humility, calm, wisdom, patience, objectivity, and trust (Mineo, 2014; Ljungblom, 2012; Kinsey, 2010; Kupfer, 2007; Vera & Rodriguez, 2004). They are as follows:

1. **Humility:** It is an ethical attribute of how to think better about business and achieve integration between the individual and society, and its relative availability is high and other times appear low. And is influenced by the personality of the individual and surrounding circumstances, and humility has many difficulties to judge the availability of leadership.
2. **Calmness:** It is considered a rare quality in human life, due to the ramifications of life, the abundance of work and the surrounding problems. The calm feature plays an important role in leadership, especially when making crucial decisions. The calm helps the leader to think deeply and in a better way to solve difficult problems. In addition, careful consideration gives consideration to the subject in all its aspects, thus enhancing the best solutions to the problems and challenges of the work.
3. **Wisdom:** It refers to a balance between available resources and business requirements, both behavioral and material. Wisdom is an advanced stage of thinking based on the objective study of what the decision is. Wisdom is also often associated with best decisions in the case of limited resources or time and others.
4. **Patience:** It is one of the most important characteristics that must be accompanied by LL as it relates to achieving short-term goals. This is due to the leader's desire to reflect his ideas in the work environment. Patience is important for leadership, since achieving success does not only mean possessing the enthusiasm, energy, knowledge, or effort to do so. Rather, it requires skillful patience based on a high managerial insight. And hard work can not be achieved without patience, and patience makes the commander is able to deal with organizational problems as well as to act wisely during crises and what it takes to promote the reality of individuals within the organization.
5. **Objectivity:** It relates to rationality in behavior, objectivity enables the leader to possess the minds of individuals and influence their behavior, and objectivity is one of the most outstanding features of scientific thinking methods. Objectivity relates to the individual's thinking about the problem and to trying to think about solving it in a clear and systematic way.
6. **Trust:** The success of the leader in his field depends on his ability to create high levels of trust between him and the people working in the organization, as this increases the link between the individual on the one hand and their bosses on the other, which contributes to the organizational success.

3. Organizational Reputation

3.1. Organizational Reputation Concept

OR is a combination of factors that combine to achieve a positive response to crises (Schnitzetzand & Epstein, 2005).

OR is the respect and credibility of relationships among the staff of the organization. The way people deal with them or the moral commitment to society affects the reputation of the organization. The organization's reputation relates to the extent to which it achieves material gains and creates innovative practices in its field of work (Ettenson, & Knowles , 2008).

OR is the sum of the value attained by the organization through its multiple market objectives (Gumus & Oksuz, 2009).

OR is an intangible asset over a period of time, and its image is determined by the value obtained by stakeholders and the degree of trust they have with the organization (Marcellis-Warin & Teodoresco, 2012).

OR is a key element in building confidence in the organization, which results in the achievement of core values, as well as transparency and commitment to work risk (Beheshtifar & Korouki, 2013).

3.2. Organizational Reputation Dimensions

The dimensions of OR are creativity, social responsibility, and quality of service (Sontaite & Kristensen, 2009). It can be explained as follows:

1. **Creativity:** It is essential to the development of any organization and is achieved not only through products and services, but through management practices. Organization should rely on creativity based on competencies and management skills and its impact on decision-making (Nogueira & Marques, 2008).
Creativity is the ability to create something new and bring it into existence. Creativity is an interactive social process that can excite emotions among workers, and it leads to efficient and effective work (Biniari, 2011).
2. **Social Responsibility:** It reflects the behavior and personal values of business managers, which are the beliefs and attitudes that lead them to form a basis for their information and to adopt their own behavior (Tari, 2011).
Social responsibility is the commitment and commitment of business people to follow policies to make decisions, address desired situations and achieve goals and values within society. Social responsibility is not only to focus on maximizing profits as a single goal of the organization and to be motivated by the moral and moral commitment of decision makers in the organization (Alshbiel & Alawawdeh, 2011).

3. **Quality of Service:** It means the degree to which the service meets the needs of customers, because we live in a turbulent environment, and the high level of competition between business organizations, whether related to the production of goods or the provision of services. As organizations entered global markets, the process of selecting a product or service became more extensive for the customer, prompting organizations to pay attention to increasing the quality of their products and to doing business that allows the organization to design products that meet customer needs (Hueiju & Fang, 2009).

4. Research Model

The proposed comprehensive conceptual model is presented in Figure (1). The diagram below shows that there is one independent variable for the study of LL. There is one dependent variable OR.

The research framework suggests that LL has an impact on OR at the Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

LL as measured consisted of humility, calmness, wisdom, patience, objectivity, and trust (Mineo, 2014; Ljungblom, 2012; Kinsey, 2010; Kupfer, 2007; Vera & Rodriguez, 2004).

OR is measured in the terms creativity, social responsibility, and quality of service (Sontaite & Kristensen, 2009).

Figure (1)
Proposed Comprehensive Conceptual Model

5. Research Questions

The researcher reached the research problem through two sources. The first source is to be found in previous studies, and it turns out that there is a lack in the number of literature review that dealt with the analysis of the relationship between LL and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt. This called for the researcher to test this relationship in the Egyptian environment.

The second source is the pilot study, which was conducted an interview with (30) employees at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt to identify the dimensions of LL and OR. The researcher found through the pilot study several indicators notably the blurred important and vital role that could be played by LL in building OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt. The research questions of this study are as follows:

- Q1: What is the relationship between LL (Humility) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt?
- Q2: What is the nature of the relationship between LL (Calmness) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt?
- Q3: What is the extent of the relationship between LL (Wisdom) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt?
- Q4: What is the relationship between LL (Patience) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt?
- Q5: What is the nature of the relationship between LL (Objectivity) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt?
- Q6: What is the extent of the relationship between LL (Trust) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt?

6. Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were developed to decide if there is a significant correlation between LL and OR.

- H1: There is no relationship between LL (Humility) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.
- H2: LL (Calmness) has no statistical significant effect on OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

- H3: There is no relationship between LL (Wisdom) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.
 H4: There is no relationship between LL (Patience) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.
 H5: LL (Objectivity) has no significant effect on OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.
 H6: There is no relationship between LL (Trust) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

7. Research Population and Sample

The population of the study included all employees at the pharmaceutical industry in Egypt. This sector includes five companies. They are Delta for the Pharmaceutical Industry, Egyptian International Pharmaceutical Industries (Eipico), Pharma Sweden, Egypt Otsu, and Egyptian Chemicals and Drugs. This explains why the population of this study includes 4,783 employees. The random sampling was used for collecting the primary data as it was difficult to get all of the items of the research population because of time limitations. The stratified random sample was used while selecting items from the different categories of employees. The following equation determines the sampling size (Daniel, 1999):

$$n = \frac{N \times (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}{d^2(N-1) + (Z)^2 \times P(1-P)}$$

Accordingly, the sample size has become 356 employees at the pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

Table (1) Distribution of the Sample Size

Egyptian Pharmaceutical Companies in Egypt	Employees	Percentage	Sample Size
1. Delta for the Pharmaceutical Industry	1500	31.4%	356X 31.4% = 112
2. Egyptian International Pharmaceutical Industries (Eipico)	1833	38.3%	356X 38.3% = 136
3. Pharma Sweden	850	17.8%	356 17.8% = 63
4. Egypt Otsu	350	7.3%	356X 7.3% = 26
5. Egyptian Chemicals and Drugs	250	5.2%	356X 5.2% = 19
Total	4783	100%	356X 100% = 356

Source: Personnel Department at Pharmaceutical Industry in Egypt, 2018

Descriptive statistics are used to describe some of the features of the respondents at the pharmaceutical industry in Egypt who participated in the survey. Table (2) provides more detailed information about the sample and the measures.

Table (2) Characteristics of Items of the Sample

Variables	Number	Percentage
1- Job Title	Physicians	120 42%
	Nurses	135 47%
	Administrative Staff	30 11%
	Total	285 100%
2- Sex	Male	110 39%
	Female	175 61%
	Total	285 100%
3- Marital Status	Single	100 35%
	Married	185 65%
	Total	285 100%
4- Age	Under 30	110 39%
	From 30 to 45	100 35%
	Above 45	75 26%
	Total	285 100%
5- Educational Level	University	185 65%
	Post Graduate	100 35%
	Total	285 100%
6- Period of Experience	Less than 5 years	90 32%
	From 5 to 10	80 28%
	More than 10	115 40%
	Total	285 100%

8. Data Collection

The researcher was used the questionnaire for collecting data. The questionnaire is interested in LL and OR at pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

The survey included three questions. The first is related to LL, the second detects OR, the third relates to the demographic variables of employees at the pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

About 356 questionnaires were distributed. 285 usable questionnaires. The response rate was 80%.

The research depend on the Likert scale for each statement ranging from (5) “full agreement,” (4) for “agree,” (3) for “neutral,” (2) for “disagree,” and (1) for “full disagreement.”

9. Data Analysis and Hypotheses Testing

9.1. Coding of variables

The main variables, sub-variables, and methods of measuring variables can be explained in the following table:

Table (3)
Description and Measuring of the Research Variables

Main Variables		Sub-Variables	Number of Statement	Methods of Measuring Variables
Independent Variable	Lean Leadership	Humility	3	Mineo, 2014; Ljungblom, 2012; Kinsey, 2010; Kupfer, 2007; Vera & Rodriguez, 2004
		Calmness	2	
		Wisdom	3	
		Patience	2	
		Objectivity	4	
		Trust	4	
Total LL			18	
Dependent Variable	Organizational Reputation	Creativity	4	Sontaite & Kristensen, 2009
		Social Responsibility	4	
		Quality of Service	4	
		Total OR		

9.2. Descriptive Analysis

Table (4): shows the mean and standard deviations of LL and OR

Variables	The Dimension	Mean	Standard Deviation
LL	Humility	3.89	0.825
	Calmness	4.02	0.903
	Wisdom	3.95	0.917
	Patience	4.20	0.850
	Objectivity	3.88	0.824
	Trust	4.03	0.791
	Total Measurement		3.98
OR	Creativity	3.50	0.739
	Social Responsibility	3.69	0.675
	Quality of Service	3.51	0.617
	Total Measurement		3.52

Source: SPSS, V.23, 2015

According to Table (4), among the various facets of LL, most of the respondents identified the presence of humility ($M=3.89$, $SD=0.825$), calmness ($M=4.02$, $SD=0.903$), wisdom ($M=3.95$, $SD=0.917$), patience ($M=4.20$, $SD=0.850$), objectivity ($M=3.88$, $SD=0.824$), trust ($M=4.03$, $SD=0.791$), and total LL ($M=3.98$, $SD=0.721$).

The second issue examined was the different facets of OR. Most of the respondents identified the presence of creativity ($M=3.50$, $SD=0.739$), social responsibility ($M=3.69$, $SD=0.675$), quality of service ($M=3.51$, $SD=0.617$), and total OR ($M=3.52$, $SD=0.648$).

9.3. Evaluating Reliability

Data analysis was conducted. All scales were first subjected to reliability analysis. Cronbach’s Alpha was used to assess the reliability of the scales. Item analysis indicated that dropping any item from the scales would not significantly raise the alphas.

Table (5): Reliability of LL and OR

Variables	Dimension	Number of Statement	ACC
LL	Humility	3	0.793
	Calmness	2	0.703
	Wisdom	3	0.741
	Patience	2	0.613
	Objectivity	4	0.820
	Trust	4	0.721
	Total Measurement	18	0.936
OR	Creativity	4	0.931
	Social Responsibility	4	0.915
	Quality of Service	4	0.884
	Total Measurement	12	0.965

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

To assess the reliability of the data, Cronbach's Alpha test was conducted. Table (5) shows the reliability results for LL and OR. All items had alphas above 0.70 and were therefore excellent, according to Langdridge's (2004) criteria. Table (5) presents the reliability of LL. The reliabilities of humility, calmness, wisdom, patience, objectivity, trust are generally higher. The 18 items of LL are reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.936. The humility, which consists of 3 items, is reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.793. The 2 items related to calmness, are reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.703 while the 3 items of wisdom are reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.741. The patience, which consists of 2 items, is reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.613. The 4 items related to objectivity, are reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.820 while the 4 items of trust are reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.721. Thus, the internal consistency of LL can be acceptable.

According to Table (5), the 12 items of OR are reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.965. The creativity, which consists of 4 items, is reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.931. The 4 items related to social responsibility are reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.915 while the 4 items of quality of service are reliable because the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.884. Thus, the internal consistency of OR can be acceptable.

9.4. The Means, St. Deviations, and Correlation among Variables

Table (6): Means, Standard Deviations and Intercorrelations among Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	LL	OR
Lean Leadership	3.98	0.721	1	
Organizational Reputation	3.52	0.648	0.698**	1

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Table (6) shows correlation coefficients between the research variables, and results indicate the presence of significant correlation between variables (LL, and OR). The level of LL is high (Mean=3.98; SD=0.721), while OR is (Mean=3.52; SD=0.648).

9.5. The Correlation between LL and OR

The relationship between LL and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt is presented in the following table:

Table (7): Correlation Matrix between LL and OR

Research Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Humility	1						
Calmness	0.810**	1					
Wisdom	0.445**	0.665**	1				
Patience	0.528**	0.718**	0.843**	1			
Objectivity	0.958**	0.830**	0.458**	0.526**	1		
Trust	0.476**	0.712**	0.958**	0.833**	0.497**	1	
Organizational Reputation	0.707**	0.577**	0.529**	0.514**	0.688**	0.530**	1

Note: ** Correlation is significant at 0.01 level

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

Based on the Table (7), correlation between LL (humility) and OR is 0.707. For LL (calmness) and OR, the value is 0.577 whereas LL (wisdom) and OR shows correlation value of 0.529. Also, correlation between LL (patience) and OR is 0.514. For LL (objectivity) and OR, the value is 0.688 whereas LL (trust) and OR shows correlation value of 0.530. The overall correlation between LL and OR is 0.698.

9.6. Lean Leadership (Humility) and OR

The relationship between LL (humility) and OR is determined. The first hypothesis to be tested is:

H1: There is no relationship between LL (Humility) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

Table (8): MRA Results for LL (Humility) and OR

The Variables of LL (Humility)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I treat people appropriately who have not carried out tasks well	0.364**	0.595	0.354
2. I even delegate prestigious tasks	0.251**	0.586	0.343
3. I aim to reach agreements on what must be done	0.237**	0.606	0.367
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.712	
		0.507	
		96.400	
		3, 281	
		3.78	
		0.000	
** P < .01			

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (8) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.712 demonstrating that the 3 independent variables of LL (humility) construe OR significantly. The three independent variables of LL (humility) can explain 51% of the total factors in OR level. Hence, 49% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.7. Lean Leadership (Calmness) and OR

The relationship between LL (calmness) and OR is determined. The second hypothesis to be tested is:

H2: LL (Calmness) has no statistical significant effect on OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

Table (9) MRA Results for LL (Calmness) and OR

The Variables of LL (Calmness)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I keep calm in stressful situations	0.339**	0.513	0.263
2. I demonstrate positive thinking in stressful situations	0.318**	0.504	0.254
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.578	
		0.334	
		70.710	
		2, 282	
		4.60	
		0.000	
** P < .01			

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (9) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.578. This means that LL has been significantly explained by the 2 independent variables of LL (calmness). The two independent variables of LL (calmness) justified only 33% of the total factors in OR level. Hence, 67% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.8. Lean Leadership (Wisdom) and OR

The relationship between LL (Wisdom) and OR is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

H3: There is no relationship between LL (Wisdom) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt

Table (10): MRA Results for LL (Wisdom) and OR

The Variables of LL (Wisdom)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I show insight into people's needs	0.119*	0.399	0.150
2. I can deal with troublesome co-workers	0.430**	0.544	0.295
3. I make good decisions under pressure, even when lacking full information	0.122*	0.381	0.145
▪ MCC		0.573	
▪ DC		0.328	
▪ Calculated F		45.673	
▪ Degree of Freedom		3, 281	
▪ Indexed F		3.78	
▪ Level of Significance		0.000	
** P < .01	* P < .05		

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (10) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.573 demonstrating that the 3 independent variables of LL (wisdom) construe OR significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, 3 independent variables of LL (wisdom) can explain only 32% of the total factors in OR level. Hence, 68% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.9. Lean Leadership (Patience) and OR

The relationship between LL (patience) and OR is determined. The fourth hypothesis to be tested is:

H4: There is no relationship between LL (Patience) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

Table (11): MRA Results for LL (Patience) and OR

The Variables of LL (Patience)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I take time to listen	0.124*	0.342	0.116
2. I am good at dealing with diffuse and unclear situations	0.489**	0.544	0.295
▪ MCC		0.555	
▪ DC		0.308	
▪ Calculated F		62.858	
▪ Degree of Freedom		2, 282	
▪ Indexed F		4.60	
▪ Level of Significance		0.000	
** P < .01			

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (11) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.555 demonstrating that the 2 independent variables of LL (patience) construe OR significantly. The two independent variables of LL (patience) can explain 31% of the total factors in OR level. Hence, 69% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.10. Lean Leadership (Objectivity) and OR

The relationship between LL (Objectivity) and OR is determined. The fifth hypothesis to be tested is:

H5: LL (Objectivity) has no significant effect on OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

Table (12) MRA Results for LL (Objectivity) and OR

The Variables of LL (Objectivity)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I give others constructive feedback	0.283**	0.513	0.263
2. I tackle relationship problems	0.202**	0.586	0.343
3. I act cost-effectively	0.255**	0.606	0.367
4. I contribute to the good reputation of the unit in the organization	0.128*	0.524	0.274
▪ MCC		0.697	
▪ DC		0.485	
▪ Calculated F		66.028	
▪ Degree of Freedom		4, 280	
▪ Indexed F		3.31	
▪ Level of Significance		0.000	
** P < .01			

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (12) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.697. This means that LL has been significantly explained by the 4 independent variables of LL (objectivity). The four independent variables of LL (objectivity) justified only 48% of the total factors in OR level. Hence, 52% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

9.11. Lean Leadership (Trust) and OR

The relationship between LL (Trust) and OR is determined. The third hypothesis to be tested is:

H6: There is no relationship between LL (Trust) and OR at Pharmaceutical industry in Egypt.

Table (13): MRA Results for LL (Trust) and OR

The Variables of LL (Trust)	Beta	R	R ²
1. I take co-workers opinions into consideration	0.075	0.329	0.108
2. I contribute to others enjoyment of their job, which encourages them to work harder	0.094*	0.331	0.109
3. I make others feel they share responsibility for the unit's development	0.119*	0.399	0.159
4. I am the person to turn to for advice on issues in my field of work	0.414**	0.544	0.295
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ MCC ▪ DC ▪ Calculated F ▪ Degree of Freedom ▪ Indexed F ▪ Level of Significance 		0.573	
		0.329	
		34.276	
		4, 280	
		3.31	
		0.000	
** P < .01 * P < .05			

Source: The researcher based on the outputs of SPSS, V.23, 2015

As Table (13) proves, the MRA resulted in the R of 0.573 demonstrating that the 4 independent variables of LL (trust) construe OR significantly. Furthermore, the value of R square, 4 independent variables of LL (trust) can explain only 33% of the total factors in LL level. Hence, 67% are explained by the other factors. Therefore, there is enough empirical evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

10. Research Results

By reviewing the results of descriptive analysis of the data on which the study was based and testing the research hypothesis, the study reached a set of results which will be reviewed and discussed as follows:

1. The results of the data analysis indicated that the relationship between LL and OR was positive. This means that the employees awareness which has a good LL, lowers their feelings about their belonging to that organization. This is directly reflected in increasing their commitment and thus achieving the good reputation of the organization.
2. The employees in the organization realize that the organization is the place where they work. Therefore they try to maintain the reputation of the organization through their commitment, and they do not wish to detract from the organization in any way. This is because they consider themselves to be an important part of the fabric of the organization and are proud of it.
3. The analysis showed that the change in the level of employee awareness of LL is reflected in further levels of organizational reputation enhancement by employees.
4. The analysis showed that the change in the availability of LL is reflected in the further change in the levels of organizational commitment of employees and this effect also leads to a change in organizational reputation levels.

11. Recommendations

In the light of the previous results, the researcher concluded with a set of recommendations as follows:

1. The necessity of investing the organization in the abilities of the employees in terms of the availability of the LL by respecting the capabilities of the employees of the organization such as finding a wage system commensurate with their efforts and urging participation in decision making within the organization.
2. Adopting effective communication methods that enhance the importance of distinguished employees and build a system through which values can be established among the employees within the organization, and the need to be committed to exchanging positive respect for the characteristics of the employees and avoiding all that contributes to reducing the personal status of the employee.
3. The need for the organization to reflect a positive image of the members of society by disseminating positive information about its good reputation. The dissemination of information through seminars and conferences can enhance the employees' awareness of the status of the organization in society in general.
4. The organization should focus on the importance of social values in the organization and the need for employees to feel proud when their personal values dissolve in social values, which enhance their levels of commitment to the organization.

5. Develop an appropriate strategy to manage and consolidate the concepts of LL, OR and highlight its importance, programs and applications through training programs, panel discussions, seminars and scientific conferences.
6. The organization should pay attention to the process of creating a common vision among employees to enhance OR through LL, and encourage employees to make suggestions to develop their abilities and improve their performance, which makes the organization in a distinguished position compared to others in the same field.

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